

TROPHIC AND FUNCTIONAL CONSEQUENCES OF HARMFUL CYANOBACTERIAL BLOOMS IN RESERVOIR ECOSYSTEMS

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Abstract

Harmful cyanobacterial blooms alter trophic interactions in freshwater ecosystems by reducing the efficiency of energy transfer to higher trophic levels. Cyanobacterial dominance leads to a decline in large-bodied zooplankton, particularly *Daphnia*, weakening grazing pressure and promoting bloom persistence. As a result, a substantial fraction of primary production is diverted into the microbial loop, limiting energy availability for fish and disrupting trophic coupling. In the Dnipro River reservoirs, these effects are intensified by hydrological regulation, nutrient enrichment, and, under current conditions, war-related disturbances. These processes contribute to trophic instability and highlight the need for integrated monitoring approaches.

Keywords: harmful algal blooms, cyanobacteria, trophic interactions, microbial loop, freshwater ecosystems, Dnipro reservoirs, eutrophication

Harmful cyanobacterial blooms fundamentally alter trophic structure in freshwater ecosystems by reducing the efficiency of energy transfer to higher trophic levels, including fish and piscivorous predators [1, 3]. A key response of zooplankton communities to cyanobacterial dominance is the decline of large-bodied filter feeders, particularly species of the genus *Daphnia* [2]. This shift weakens grazing pressure on phytoplankton and promotes further bloom persistence. Under such conditions, a substantial fraction of phytoplankton biomass becomes inaccessible to consumers due to its low nutritional quality and morphological resistance to filtration [3, 9]. The unconsumed portion of primary production is redirected into the dissolved organic matter pool and subsequently processed through the microbial loop [1], where bacterial pathways dominate its transformation. As a result, the proportion of energy reaching higher trophic levels declines, leading to a mismatch between peaks in food availability and the energetic demands of different fish life stages [1, 3, 9].

In parallel, cyanotoxins are transferred across trophic levels [5, 8, 9], affecting fish physiology by reducing growth rates, survival, reproductive capacity, and immune function. These processes ultimately influence the availability and stability of food resources for piscivorous birds.

In the reservoirs of the Dnipro River cascade, hydrological regulation combined with elevated nutrient inputs creates conditions conducive to persistent cyanobacterial development. Bloom intensity is governed by the interaction between thermal regime and nutrient availability, particularly phosphorus, whose limiting role diminishes as concentrations increase [13]. In the Kanev Reservoir, this is reflected in pronounced seasonal peaks of phytoplankton biomass associated with fluctuations in nutrient loads and hydrological conditions [14]. In contrast, the Kyiv Reservoir exhibits marked spatial and temporal heterogeneity in cyanobacterial development [10, 12].

For fish communities, these dynamics translate into variable feeding conditions and consequent restructuring of assemblage composition, while for piscivorous birds they result in unstable and unpredictable foraging habitats. Importantly, under wartime conditions, additional pressures emerge through disruption of hydrological regimes caused by damage to hydraulic infrastructure. These disturbances affect primary producer communities [6] and drive further reorganization of fish assemblages [7], thereby amplifying trophic instability.

Taken together, these processes highlight the need for integrated research on physiological and biochemical responses of aquatic organisms, spatial patterns of ecosystem functioning, and the development of monitoring and management approaches aimed at mitigating the impacts of harmful cyanobacterial blooms.

References

- Cotner, J.B., & Biddanda, B.A. (2002). Small players, large role: microbial influence on biogeochemical processes in pelagic aquatic ecosystems. *Ecosystems*, 5, 105–121. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-001-0059-3>
- DeMott, W.R., Gulati, R.D., & Van Donk, E. (2001). Daphnia food limitation in three hypereutrophic Dutch lakes. *Limnology and Oceanography*, 46, 2054–2060. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lo.2001.46.8.2054>
- Ger, K.A., Hansson, L.-A., & Lüring, M. (2014). Understanding cyanobacteria–zooplankton interactions in a more eutrophic world. *Freshwater Biology*, 59, 1783–1798. <https://doi.org/10.1111/fwb.12393>
- Ger, K.A., Urrutia-Cordero, P., Frost, P.C., et al. (2016). The interaction between cyanobacteria and zooplankton in a more eutrophic world. *Harmful Algae*, 54, 128–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hal.2016.02.004>
- Ibelings, B.W., Bruning, K., De Jonge, J., et al. (2005). Distribution of microcystins in a lake food web. *Microbial Ecology*, 49, 487–500. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-004-0014-x>
- Nezbrytska, I., Bilous, O., Sereda, T., et al. (2024). Effects of war-related human activities on microalgae and macrophytes in freshwater ecosystems: a case study of the Irpin River basin, Ukraine. *Water*, 16, 3604. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16243604>
- Prychepa, M.V., Kovalenko, Y.O., Nezbrytska, I.M., et al. (2025). Structure and distribution of ichthyofauna in the Irpin River basin after the hostilities' cessation. *Hydrobiological Journal*, 61(1), 13–27. <https://doi.org/10.1615/HydrobJ.v61.i1.20>
- Sotton, B., Guillard, J., Anneville, O., et al. (2013). Trophic transfer of microcystins in freshwater food webs. *Environmental Pollution*, 178, 98–104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2013.02.023>
- Wilson, A.E., Sarnelle, O., & Tillmanns, A.R. (2006). Effects of cyanobacterial toxicity and morphology on zooplankton population growth. *Limnology and Oceanography*, 51, 1915–1924. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lo.2006.51.4.1915>
- Vyshnevskiy, V.I. (2019). Spatial and temporal variability of water “blooming” in Dnipro reservoirs. *Ukrainian Journal of Remote Sensing of the Earth*, 18–27.
- Kruzhylina, S.V. (2015). Development level of hydrobionts as an indicator of feeding conditions for fish in Dnipro reservoirs. *Fisheries Science of Ukraine*, 15–30. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15407/fsu2015.04.015>
- Kurovska, L.V. (2024). Eutrophication of the Kyiv Reservoir (Ukraine): a review. *Biological Systems: Theory and Innovation*, 15(1), 61–72.
- Shcherbak, V.I., Semeniuk, N.Ye., & Maistrova, N.V. (2026). Water “blooming” in upper Dnipro reservoirs under current conditions. *Reports of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine*.
- Shcherbak, V.I., Yakushin, V.M., Zadorozhnaya, A.M., et al. (2016). Seasonal and interannual dynamics of phytoplankton, phytomicroepiphyton, and nutrient content in the river section of the Kanev Reservoir. *Hydrobiological Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1615/HydrobJ.v52.i1.50>

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